

PROBLEMS OF SOCIAL INTERACTION OF TEACHERS AND STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF COOPERATION

Shyrbacheva Gulchekhira Shakirovna

PhD, head of the "Pedagogy and psychology of preschool education" Department
Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7615710>

Abstract. *In this article, the social interaction of teachers and students in a higher educational institution is revealed as the result of mutually agreed single actions that cause a feedback and include the goals of the activity, the social situation represented by the means of education and the atmosphere of the university. In the process of which teachers and students try to understand or more accurately "unravel" each other's intentions by analyzing their actions and relying on their past experience in similar situations.*

Keywords: *social interaction, standardization of relations, teacher and student, symbolic environment, subject-subject nature of relations, social roles, norm, problem, teacher's image.*

The essence of social interaction lies in the fact that only in interaction with other people can a person satisfy the vast majority of his needs, interests, values.

The interaction of the subjects of the educational process is the result of mutually coordinated single actions that cause a feedback and include the goals of the activity, the social situation represented by the means of education and the atmosphere of the university.

Higher education is "created" by the procedures of interaction between participants in the educational process, each of which is both a subject pursuing common goals and an object of orientation for other actors. Regular reproduction of situations of interaction leads to the standardization of expectations and the formation of norms that structure interaction models and define social roles. Differences in the mutual expectations of teachers and students cover a wide range of problems - from value orientations to the quality of the knowledge gained and the effectiveness of their assimilation.

In the process of interaction, teachers and students try to understand or more accurately "unravel" each other's intentions by analyzing their actions and relying on their past experience in similar situations. The social world of students is formed as a result of social interactions with each other and with teachers. At the same time, the symbolic environment has a decisive influence on students. It contributes to the formation of their consciousness and the human "I". The attitude of teachers to work, to others, high professionalism, erudition, self-discipline, the desire for creativity contribute to the formation of such qualities in the student environment. It is intelligence, sociability, tact that create such an atmosphere of relations between teachers and students, when the latter become equal subjects of a single process of education and upbringing, self-development, socio-cultural self-determination.

Higher education is becoming more vital due to the transition from rigid systems of organization, where the priority of submission and coercion takes place, to more flexible and mediated ones (consent and compulsion), in which some subjects get the opportunity to consciously act in accordance with the expectations of others.

The subject - the subjective nature of the interaction of participants in the educational process determines the relevance of such personality traits as good manners, courtesy, charm. The

principle constituting communication assumes that "everyone should give the other the same maximum values of communication (joy, lightness, liveliness) that are compatible with the maximum values that he himself received."

This principle points to the democratic structure of communication between equal partners, and the process of interaction acts as a social partnership. The content of interaction in the field of higher education is a realizing form of unity between teachers and students based on the embodiment of their motives and interests.

In the field of higher education, the installation of the same approach to all students prevails. This order is fixed institutionally. Consolidation of a respectful attitude towards the teacher is a mandatory rule for expecting a polite attitude from the student. This rule should also be observed by teachers when interacting with students. Mutual refraction of social norms and values in the minds of participants in the educational process, its comprehension and reflection in the real actions of teachers and students determines the dominant personality-oriented approach in educational activities.

Increasing the degree of satisfaction from the interaction process includes ensuring the degree of comfort in the system of mutual actions, adequate perception of oneself and the partner in interaction. The expected result of joint activities is determined by the presence of a common goal that meets the interests of everyone and contributes to the realization of the needs of everyone, the means and conditions for achieving it, and the level of qualification of the teaching staff.

The unity of the purpose of the interaction of subjects of education, due to the coincidence of their social positions and interests, will not provide reliable mutual understanding if the participants in the educational process are not guided by the rules and norms shared by all.

The process of mutual understanding plays a big role in the communication between teachers and students, it makes their behavior predictable. When a stable mutual understanding is established between the participants in the educational process, formal and informal roles are formed that determine the behavior of each subject of interaction. Thus, social interaction turns out to be a product of the performance of roles that subjects of higher education receive from the outside and internalize. The individual determines his position in relation to others, his status in the social structure, his social roles, which prescribe certain patterns of behavior to him and make interaction predictable.

The central problem in interaction is the problem of the relationship of participants regarding the acquisition of professional knowledge, skills and abilities. Each participant enters the social situation with some accumulated experience and cultural background supposedly shared by all. Cognitive, normative prerequisites and self-limitations shared by all participants are the basis of the order of interaction.

From the first days of study at the university, students begin to form common features of the teacher's image. To create a stable and positive interaction with students, teachers have to make a lot of efforts, each of them needs to strive to create their own positive image. Psychologists say that the most powerful component in the formation of students' opinions about the teacher is his assessment during the first meeting. It is the impression received during the first contact that leaves the longest and most stable imprint on further face-to-face interaction.

There can hardly be any doubt that the image of a teacher that students develop actively influences various aspects of interaction and cooperation with him. The effectiveness of the educational process largely depends on how adequate the teacher is to the situation and how accurately students perceive him.

Consideration of the problem of social interaction between teachers and students is a search for answers to a wide variety of questions: what are the typical ways in which subjects of higher education establish a wide variety of connections among themselves; how they maintain these connections; what are the conditions for maintaining and breaking these links.

REFERENCES

1. Simmel G. The problem of sociology. Communication. An example of pure or formal sociology // Theoretical sociology: Anthology. In 2 hours / Per. from eng., fr. Compiler and general editor of the joint venture. Bankovsky. M. Book House "University" - Part 1
2. Lykova, V. A. Conceptual foundations of competence-based approach in the preparation of a teacher of higher education / V. A. Lykova, I. Babin // Slavyan. ped. culture. - 2006. - No. 5. - P. 105–107.
3. Slastenin, V. A. The quality of education as a socio-pedagogical phenomenon / V. A. Slastenin // Ped. education and science. - 2005. - No. 3. - P. 65–69.
4. Tatur, Yu. G. Competence approach in describing the results and designing standards of higher professional education: materials on the second session of the methodological seminar: author's version / Yu. G. Tatur. - M., 2004. - 16 p.
5. Filippov, V. M. Tasks of modernization of education at the present stage / V. M. Filippov // Higher. education today. - 2003. - No. 3. - S. 2–5.